

Just Walk Out Technology in Hypermarkets

Ar.S. Santhana Divyaa,

M.Arch (construction project management) student
Faculty of Architecture, Dr. M.G.R Educational and
Research Institution
Chennai, India

Ar. V. Vidya, Ar. B.A. Mookambika
Associate Professor, Faculty of Architecture
Dr. M.G.R Educational and Research Institution
Chennai, India

Abstract:- The retail industry has undergone significant changes in the last ten years as a result of digitalization and technological advancement, and retailers have had to adapt by putting new business models and competitive strategies in place to meet the needs of their customers. The sector has been impacted by numerous new trends over the past few decades, including the emergence of supermarkets, the onset of e-commerce, the introduction of cashier-less stores, and more. In the latter, human involvement is minimized through the use of cameras, sensors, and self-shelving units. This is a new form of store that is entirely computer-based and digitalized. The introduction of Amazon Go, this growing idea was first introduced by Amazon, but other start-up businesses are quickly embracing the difficulty. The online retailer Amazon runs a chain of Amazon Go convenience stores in the United States and the United Kingdom. Nowadays, no one likes waiting in line at the register when shopping. Amazon developed automated Go stores that incorporate computer vision, deep learning algorithms, and sensor fusion for the buy, checkout, and payment phases involved in the retail transaction to automate this process. There are 32 stores in the United States as of March 2021 (both announced and established), and there are 15 in the United Kingdom. We shall examine every facet of this technology in this essay. This essay aims to examine customer knowledge of cashier-less stores and the applicability of many aspects of this novel type of store.

Keywords:- Amazon Go, Deep Learning, Computer Vision, Sensor, Aws, Rl, Technology.

I. INTRODUCTION

To boost velocity, connection, and availability of use, we have seen a developing trend involving new technologies and a rising level of service automation during the past ten years. There is a tendency to lessen the need for human intervention and control in carrying out various processes, even though the areas of application are diverse. Therefore, the typical objective when implementing new technologies is to reduce the quantity of labor and the number of workers by employing advanced algorithms that can complete specific tasks faster than a human. Additionally, the pandemic situation has sparked accelerations and alterations, beginning with consumer behavior.

This condition, which is related to the rapid spread of various shopping channels, poses new obstacles for end users as well as retailers, who must adjust to the new, complicated

environment to stay competitive in a globalized world where the most important factor is customer pleasure. The retail industry has seen a full transformation in this highly competitive environment over the past few decades, from the emergence of supermarkets to the introduction of e-commerce and, ultimately, the adoption of the omnichannel strategy to meet the needs of both online and offline consumers. Future technological advancements and innovations that give customers fresh, satisfying shopping experiences will present merchants with several hurdles.

A group of Amazon executives created a 15,000-square-foot dummy supermarket in a rented warehouse in Seattle to test the concept of Amazon Go stores. A store that doesn't need customers to wait in queue or pay at the register is known as a cashier-less store (also known as a till-less store, checkout-free store, or just walk-out store). To track which things are picked up or returned, stores use a variety of technologies, including cameras, sensors, computer vision algorithms, and deep learning. Minute Maid Park in Houston, Texas, installed Amazon's technology at two of its concession stands in April 2022 to make it the first Major League Baseball stadium to use cashier-less retail.

The cashier-less concept, in which human interaction is drastically reduced in fully automated stores, is one recent innovation in technological trends. A combination of artificial intelligence, computer vision, deep learning, and edge computing enables customers to simply buy goods and leave a cashier-less store without the need to "check out" in the conventional sense after completing the registration process. Customers should be able to enter and leave cashier-less establishments as quickly and with as little human touch as feasible. This is the main objective, both from the perspective of the client and the retailer. Despite the growth of e-commerce and the rise in consumers adopting this method of buying over the past ten years, the global COVID-19 pandemic's debut immediately changed consumer behavior and made avoiding human interaction a top priority for buyers.

The article is divided into three sections: the introduction of e-commerce follows a brief theoretical overview of the retail industry, its development, and the growing significance of technological innovation. Then, from the viewpoints of both retailers and customers, a specific focus on cashier-less stores is presented.

II. STUDY METHODS

For this study, a net study technique was used to analyze several retail use cases in terms of the adoption of smart technologies like AI for smart retailing and the advantages that resulted for the organizations under discussion. Whitepapers, articles, reports, and other online databases were used to gather the data for this study. The topicality of the collected literature was next examined.

A. Online resources

The information was gathered from the internet to gain a wider understanding of this subject to keep up with technological innovation.

B. Library hunt

Information for this study was gathered from books, journals, published and unpublished student dissertations, as well as other noteworthy papers.

III. STUDY OF LITERATURE

A. Benefits and drawbacks of self-checkout systems Express self-checkout registers for retailers

One of the checkout counters kinds most often found in modern establishments is the retail checkout counter. One of the checkout counters kinds most often found in modern establishments is the retail checkout counter

➤ Space costs

Checkout counters take up far less area than registers when it comes to the expense of space. Self-checkout normally takes less time than registers, thus there is usually only one wait for many checkout counters, which frees up additional room.

Counters are one of the least cost-effective self-checkout solutions, which puts them at a disadvantage when compared to other self-checkout options.

➤ Efficiency

Here are some things to think about with self-checkout counters in terms of efficiency:

- Less waiting time than when using a cashier lane. However, the transaction pace is considerably slower than some of the other systems discussed in this article.
- Lower labor costs since one staff member can manage many self-checkout counters.
- High levels of consumer interaction: customers must scan product barcodes, place items in a bagging area, and occasionally weigh items.
- Shoplifting, in general, is a clear drawback of self-checkout. Losses can be 31% higher in a store where self-checkout accounts for 55–60% of transactions. This number is gradually declining, though, thanks to lower prices and steadily enhanced security.

➤ Customer encounter

The most important aspects influencing consumer satisfaction are transaction speed, perceived control, dependability, ease of use, and enjoyment. Given this, this

kind of checkout has an advantage over cash registers but lags behind the other technologies described below. Since self-service checkout counters have been available for some time, the majority of customers are accustomed to it.

Although self-checkout counters maximize productivity, customer satisfaction, and space use, they may be made easier to operate. According to research, the technology's main complaints from customers were the difficulty of entering goods and frequent overrides. If the technology were enhanced, self-checkout would be more popular among consumers, according to 59% of respondents.

B. Movable scanners and intelligent carts

Mobile scanners and intelligent carts are more advanced self-checkout systems than counters. Using technology that the retailer provides, they let customers scan items as they put them in their shopping basket or cart. All the customer needs to do to start shopping is to bring a smart cart or a scanner. Customers may weigh things on some smart carts thanks to built-in scales.

➤ Space costs

Mobile scanners and smart carts are more cost-effective in terms of space than counters and cash machines. They unquestionably occupy a lot less room.

➤ Efficiency

Considering the effectiveness of this method, keep the following in mind:

- Wait times are very short with this system because payment is made as soon as all items are picked up; however, it is one of the most expensive ones in terms of technology because each shopping cart and basket needs to be equipped with its scanner.

➤ Customer encounter

The key benefit of this approach is that it offers a live breakdown of the prices of all the things selected. This is a factor that adds to the usefulness and appeal of this solution.

Regarding this system, the transaction speed, perceived control, and reliability are all quite high.

Mobile scanners and smart carts can be more expensive than some of the other alternatives even though they are more effective than self-checkout stations since they require more hardware.

➤ Kiosk self-checkout systems

Self-service kiosks are frequently employed in food shops, bulkier goods like clothing, and amusement centers. The kiosks typically integrate POS hardware with food order and inventory management software when used to sell food and comparable commodities.

➤ Price of space

For pre-orders or hefty purchases when store staff is selecting the items for you, the expense of space for this solution is typically a suitable fit for fashion retail, but less so for supermarkets.

➤ *Efficiency*

In terms of effectiveness, kiosks provide the following:

- Shorter lines than when using cash registers. Pre-order or bulky purchases where store staff must collect the goods and give them to the customer are more effectively handled by these methods; they are also practical for food retail and restaurants since they allow customers to customize their orders and have a clear overview as they are adding the items.

➤ *Client encounter*

This method is more advanced than some other solutions in terms of transaction speed, but less so than others. When it comes to prepared meals and large things, it is the customer experience that is valued. Customers that use this system report feeling as in control, reliable, simple to use, and enjoyable as possible. Overall, kiosks are one of the most practical self-checkout choices for businesses offering meals, and they ought to be taken into account for various sorts of items and establishments. Online pre-ordering and checkout are the other two options.

C. *RFID scanner self-checkout gates*

To prevent the theft of commodities, we frequently see the employment of technology solutions like Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) scanner gates. However, modernizing retail is now finding a new use for RFID. Customers can walk through RFID scanner gates, scan their entire cart of groceries or other items, and check out without pausing. When a consumer pushes their cart through the gate, a list of the items is displayed on a kiosk screen. They can then pay with a card, cash, or by scanning their palm.

➤ *Price of space*

When it comes to space, RFID scanner gates are one of the most affordable options. Compared to standard self-checkout counters, they occupy significantly less space.

➤ *Efficiency*

Here are some things to think about RFID scanner gates in terms of efficiency:

- In comparison to most other self-checkout options, wait times are much shorter, and labor expenses are also decreased because one employee may supervise multiple self-checkout gates.
- With RFID scanner gates, customers may simply pay the bill and pass through the gates without having to remove the items from the cart, scan them or bag them before leaving the store.

➤ *Customer encounter*

One of the most desired in-store retail technologies, according to 72% of consumers polled for a global study, is the technology that shortens the time it takes to complete the checkout process. RFID is a perfect solution. RFID scanning is outperformed solely by scanning systems that let customers see how much money they will spend while they purchase in terms of perceived control. This self-checkout system is also among the best in terms of dependability, usability, and fun.

Retailers are effectively cutting shopping times and enhancing customer experiences with RFID tags and scanning gates. Due to the requirement of tags for all items in the store and pricey scanning gates, this self-checkout system can be quite expensive.

D. *Amazon Go's self-checkout sensors and AI*

We should not forget to mention the company that tested self-checkout sensors: Amazon Go. Sensor-equipped stores do not need registers or checkout lanes, in contrast to the majority of other self-checkout systems. Amazon combined the most sophisticated machine learning, computer vision, and AI to produce one of the best self-checkout systems. Customers scan their QR code from the smartphone app as soon as they enter the business. As the customer moves, cameras follow them and use computer vision to track what they saw. What the cameras "see" is verified by smart shelves that are fitted with a variety of sensors. Customers are immediately charged as they leave the store after adding the items to a virtual basket.

➤ *Space costs*

Self-checkout sensors are one of the most space-efficient options available because they occupy no space other than the gate that customers must pass through in every business.

➤ *Efficiency*

Here are some benefits of AI and self-checkout sensors for efficiency:

- With self-checkout sensors, checkout lines are essentially nonexistent. There is, however, a startling possible time-related drawback.
- The only checkout staff needed for this solution are those in charge of security and theft prevention, so labor costs tend to be lower.
- Because this solution does not require item scanning, it is very effective for both the customer and the retailer.

• *Customer encounter*

This solution beats out every other one in terms of transaction speed.

However, when it comes to perceived control, some customers worry about the privacy risks associated with the Amazon Go self-checkout option. To track what they purchase, customers are linked to a name (which is typical with today's self-checkout choices). They are also visually followed to observe their actions and the things they do not purchase. The idea of a business fully comprehending a customer's purchasing habits does not excite some customers. Long lines in front of new Amazon Go stores are evidence that this solution is at its pinnacle in terms of dependability, usability, and delight.

E. *Apps for mobile self-checkout using a scanner*

According to recent research, 60% of shoppers worldwide would prefer a self-service "just walk out" environment akin to Amazon Go. The mobile scan-and-go app is a more economical option that requires a far lower technological investment than self-checkout sensors. The customer installs the app, fills out their personal information,

and provides payment information to use this solution. Prices are shown and calculated as the customer selects and scans items in the store. After making a quick swipe payment in the app, the customer leaves the kiosk screen area.

➤ *Price of space*

Mobile scan-and-go apps don't need any additional area for checkout, just like self-checkout sensors like Amazon Go.

➤ *Efficiency*

Here are some mobile self-checkout factors to think about in terms of efficiency:

- There are no wait times while using mobile scanning. Queues are eliminated when a customer exits a store by scanning a code on their phone.
- Labor costs are also decreased by this system. Because very little hardware is needed and clients can use their own devices, equipment expenses are also decreased.
- Customers may scan product barcodes on the fly and obtain a clear real-time snapshot of their spending using self-checkout mobile apps.
- With this technology, shoplifting is still an issue, but intelligent scanning behavior analysis can identify potential theft.
- When compared to other systems, this one is one of the most economical, which more effectively makes up for any losses.

➤ *Customer encounter*

Customers can scan their purchases on the fly, and the cost of the items is calculated in real-time, which is one advantage this technology has over the majority of self-checkout solutions. Anywhere in the store is a good place to complete the transaction. This aspect of the solution helps to make it dependable, useful, and enjoyable to use. As the customer scans the items and can simply take them from the cart and replace them, the transaction speed is consistent with sensor-driven and RFID-type systems, increasing the perceived level of control.

➤ *Just leave technology alone.*

Simply walk away The technology tracks the items in a virtual cart and recognizes when they are taken from or put back on the shelves.

Once you're done shopping, you could just leave the store.

Immediately after, Amazon will quickly deduct the payment from the client's account and email the consumer a receipt.

This technology is currently being implemented by Amazon as Amazon Go, which provides a checkout-free shopping experience. These technologies, which include computer vision, sensing element fusion, RFID tags, and deep learning, are similar to those used in self-driving cars, face recognition systems, etc.

How Just Walk Out Technology operates following how computer vision, sensor fusion and deep learning, and RFID operate.

➤ *Sensor fusion:*

How does sensor fusion work?

To answer that question, let's look at an example: Suppose you're using GPS on your smartphone for navigation when you suddenly lose signal as you enter a tunnel. Have you ever wondered how your smartphone manages to maintain track of your location through the tunnel? It employs a method known as dead reckoning.

Your smartphone has built-in sensors, specifically accelerometers, and gyroscopes, and using the sensors and some hefty data from maths can calculate your position with surprising accuracy. Dead reckoning calculates the real-time tracking when you lose the GPS signal to calculate the position changes.

➤ *Advantages*

These are some of the benefits of sensor fusion.

- Accuracy is provided over a wide variety of operating situations by the fusion sensor.
- Multilateral, dependable, and high-level recognition devices are provided by the combined sensory data.
- Through the use of sensor fusion, a single model of the environment around a vehicle may be created using the inputs from various LIDARs, cameras, and radars. Because it balances the strengths of several sensors, the final model is more precise.
- When compared to using individual sensors, sensor fusion provides more accurate and comprehensive data.
- By extending the range of various devices, including robotics with autonomous capabilities and UAVs (unmanned aerial vehicles), sensor fusion will lower operating expenses.

➤ *Applications*

The following are some examples of sensor fusion applications.

- The Global Positioning System (GPS) and Inertial Navigation System (INS) both use sensor fusion to combine data from these systems using various methods. For instance, the extended Kalman filter is utilized to determine the attitude of an airplane using inexpensive sensors.
- The IoT (Internet of Things) has tremendous potential because sensor fusion enables context awareness.
- When several sensors are employed and perception capacity is raised, lane detection performance is substantially improved.

➤ *To learn deeply:*

Deep learning is the building of machines using methods modeled after how the human brain learns.

We just lacked the data and computing power necessary to train a machine to learn deep learning until recently.

Neural networks are what give deep learning its name; they can learn many different levels of abstraction, from simple to complex interactions.

Each layer gathers a certain type of data, rarifies it, and moves on to the next.

To build a ranked illustration, a machine using automatic facial recognition can start by looking for simple edges. The following layer may then look for varied forms, and so on. Deep learning enables this.

The machine computes the outcomes of each of these steps to identify specific objects.

GPUs are the backbone of deep learning since they process data at an extremely fast rate.

Numerous fields, including robotics, autonomous vehicles, and medical diagnosis, can benefit from deep learning.

One such important and forthcoming example of deep learning is the "just walk out" technology.

➤ *RFID*

The use of RFID technology is the most direct route for Amazon to take to realize this idea.

When a piece of stolen clothing passes across RFID sensors near a store's exit, an alarm will sound. Amazon's RFID system functions very similarly to an anti-theft RFID tag in this regard.

There is no alarm in Amazon's situation; instead, the Amazon Go app adds products to the customer's shopping basket as a result of this incident.

F. Radio Frequency Identification, or RFID, is an acronym.

An RFID device's basic operation is as follows: Without the need for a direct line of sight between the transponder and reader, RFID (radio frequency identification) enables the identification of any product or item.

The two primary hardware components that make up an RFID structure are always present.

The reader can either be a read-only device or a read-write device, depending on the system design, technology used, and necessity, and the transponder, which is positioned on the item to be scanned.

The radio frequency module, configuration-controlling unit, monitor, and antenna of an RFID reader typically work together to read RFID tags.

A few RFID readers also come with an additional interface that enables them to send the data they receive to a different system (a control system or a PC).

RFID Tag - The actual data-carrying component of an RFID structure, often made up of an electronic microchip and an antenna (coupling element).

➤ *How is RFID implemented?*

A scanning antenna, a transceiver, and a transponder are the three parts of every RFID system. An RFID reader or interrogator is the name given to the device that combines the scanning antenna and transceiver. RFID readers come in two different varieties: fixed readers and mobile readers. The RFID reader is a portable or permanently fixed network-connected device. The signals that turn on the tag are sent via radio waves. When a tag is activated, it transmits a wave back to the antenna, where it is converted into information. The RFID tag itself contains the transponder. RFID tag read range varies depending on several elements, such as tag type, reader type, RFID frequency, and interference from the environment or other RFID tags and readers. Longer read ranges are a benefit of greater power sources for tags.

➤ *Smart labels and RFID tags: what are they?*

The components of RFID tags include a substrate, an antenna, and an integrated circuit (IC). RFID inlays are the components of RFID tags that encode personal data. An RFID tag can be of two major types:

Active RFID. An active RFID tag has a power source of its own, which is frequently a battery.

RFID passive. The reading antenna's electromagnetic wave causes a current to flow through the antenna of a passive RFID tag, which is how it gets its power. Additionally, some RFID tags are semi-passive, which means that the circuitry is powered by a battery, whereas the RFID reader is used for communication. Every RFID system relies heavily on embedded low-power non-volatile memory.

Tags may be read-only or read-write, allowing for the addition of new data or the erasure of preexisting data. RFID tag read ranges differ depending on the type of tag, type of reader, RFID frequency, and interference from the environment or other RFID tags and readers. Due to the greater power supply, active RFID tags can be read over a wider area than passive RFID tags. RFID tags are basic smart labels. These labels include a barcode and an RFID tag that is attached to an adhesive label. Both RFID and barcode readers can make use of them. Unlike RFID tags, which need more sophisticated equipment, smart labels may be created on-demand using desktop printers.

➤ *What kinds of RFID systems are there?*

Low frequency (LF), high frequency (HF), and ultra-high frequency (UHF) are the three primary categories of RFID systems. Also accessible is RFID using microwaves. Countries and regions have very different frequencies.

RFID low-frequency systems. Although the common frequency is 125 KHz, these range from 30 KHz to 500 KHz. The typical transmission ranges for LF RFID are a few inches to less than six feet.

High-frequency RFID systems have a frequency range of 3 MHz to 30 MHz, with 13.56 MHz being the common HF frequency. The typical range is from a couple of inches to several feet.

RFID microwave systems. These can be read from more than 30 feet away and operate at 2.45 GHz.

The frequency will vary depending on the RFID application, and real distances may not always match expectations. For instance, the U.S. State Department stated that the RFID chips would only be able to be read from around 4 inches away when it first announced that it would begin issuing electronic passports with an RFID chip. The State Department soon learned, however, that RFID readers could read the data from the RFID tags from far farther away than 4 inches—in some cases, as far away as 33 feet. Using tags with more power can increase read ranges to more than 300 feet if longer read ranges are required.

uses for RFID

Although RFID has been around since the 1940s, the 1970s saw an increase in its application. For a very long time, widespread commercial use was restricted due to the exorbitant cost of the tags and readers. RFID use has grown as hardware costs have fallen.

Typical applications for RFID technology include:

- Inventory management,
- asset and equipment tracking,
- asset and supply chain logistics,
- inventory control,
- vehicle tracking,
- customer service,
- loss prevention,
- increased visibility
- distribution in the supply chain,
- access control in security situations,
- shipping
- healthcare
- manufacturing
- retail sales
- tap and go credit card payments

➤ *Computer vision*

Computer vision is a branch of technology that aims to make it possible for machines to perceive, find, and process images like that of human vision, then produce the desired results.

Sent sight is a fresh piece of fundamental software designed for programmers who want to incorporate computer vision-based object recognition into their applications.

Sent sight is a vision-based object recognition system that has a wide range of uses, from interactive toys to manufacturing and law enforcement.

Real-time building recognition in a city would be an example of an augmented reality application.

➤ *Application*

Additionally, image-based search applications like internet searches can utilize sent sight.

Other uses using Sent sight object recognition technologies include:

1. Image or trademark utilization search and find
2. Recognition of documents and stamps
3. Recognizing a location from a photo
4. Applications that use augmented and extended reality, including smart toys that talk to kids or can recognize specific cards or pictograms.

Applications for law enforcement include:

5. Object counting and inspection for production and logistics
6. Recognition of tattoos
7. Navigation and manipulation by robots

➤ *How does it function?*

Sent sight first identifies an object from a group of photos including the object by masking the area of the image that should be recognized. It is preferable if the object is the sole thing in the designated regions, without any of its surroundings, to avoid misclassification. Sent sight can then locate an object once it has trained and can do so in a specific frame, such as an image from a still or video camera. Sent sight can count them if a learned object appears in many places.

➤ *The Cashier-less Store*

A disruptive breakthrough called the cashier-less store allows customers to purchase goods in a store without human or automated cashiers. By introducing a system that simplifies the shopping experience and keeps track of each customer's choices and preferences without requiring the customer to do anything, a cashier-less store aims to give customers a satisfying experience, prevent time loss, and eliminate long lines and long checkout times. The novelty that cashier-less technologies provide to the retail sector is the ability for customers to walk into a store, browse and leave without having to wait in a long queue or self-checkout at the door. This has brought forth a new age in retail, especially in the grocery sector.

G. The Retail Industry's Adoption of the Cashier-less Concept and Its Acceleration During the COVID-19 Pandemic:

Being the first firm to create, test, and offer this type of store in the retail industry, Amazon invented the cashier-less concept. One of the most valuable corporations in the world, Amazon decided to launch Amazon Go a cashier-less store with cutting-edge new technologies, a few years ago. To get to this point, 5 years of testing and implementation were required. The first Amazon Go store and associated Just Walk Away app debuted in Seattle in 2018. To build 3000 new stores by the end of 2021, they subsequently launched 25 additional outlets in the US.

H. AMAZON GO STORES

Amazon unveiled Amazon Go in 2016, a physical store with several technologies designed to do away with the checkout. People need the Amazon app (formerly a dedicated Amazon Go app) to enter the store, purchase what they need, then leave so that their account will be charged thereafter.

In 2018, the first Amazon Go location opened. The first cashier-free supermarket in the United Kingdom was inaugurated by Sainsbury's in 2019. However, a few months later, it was shut down. In Kuninkaantammi, Helsinki, a Finnish company by the name of Korttelikauppa opened a store without a cashier in July 2020. The following cities saw the opening of 6 Korttelikauppa stores in the spring and summer of 2021:

- Helsinki
- Espoo
- Vantaa

Minute Maid Park in Houston, Texas, became the first Major League Baseball venue to feature cashier-free retail in April 2022. In the city of Utrecht in 2022, Aldi Nord will open the country's first store without a cashier. In Washington, DC, and Sherman Oaks, California, two Whole Foods locations will be the first to use Amazon's cashier-less technology in 2022.

I. PLATFORM OF ARCHITECTURE

The first tech deep dive on the enormous array of technologies needed to deliver the "Just Walk Out" experience was conducted at Amazon's RE: MARS conference. I'll go over everything they said with you so we can all recognize their incredible accomplishment.

➤ *Computer Vision Core: "Just Walk Out" Technology*

The computer vision-based machine learning at the center of the Go Store is utilized to automatically track and gauge each customer's intention. Surprisingly, Amazon went into great detail about how they used this technique. Although they didn't go as far as to display the precise Neural Architectures for their models, they did demonstrate the particular issues that each model addresses as well as how those issues are combined to create a more comprehensive solution.

➤ *Core Problems*

To deliver the experience, 6 fundamental issues have to be resolved.

- **Sensor Fusion:** combine signals from many sensors (or cameras, since computer vision was used exclusively to tackle this problem).
- **Calibration:** Make sure that every camera is extremely aware of where it is in the space.
- **Person detection:** Track and identify every shopper who enters the store.
- **Object Recognition:** to distinguish between the various products being sold.
- **Pose estimation:** to observe what each person doing with their arms as they approach a shelf.
- **Activity Analysis:** to identify who has picked up and who

has returned an item.

➤ *COMPONENTS NECESSARY*

➤ *Identifying Information*

The following elements are crucial for it:

- **Locator:** The "Who took What?" puzzle could not be answered by making a succession of separate picks. From the time a customer entered the store until they left, Amazon had to keep track of each customer.
- **The Locator component had to deal with issues like:**
 - a. **Occlusion,** which occurs when a person is obscured from vision by something in the store.
 - b. **The Tangled State,** where residents live near one another.
- **Linker:** After locating the consumers in the store, the next challenge was to make sure their labels were maintained across the video frames. The issues encountered during this era were:

Disambiguating Tangled States: When people are near one another, it becomes harder to tell who is who. This is dealt with by the go-store technology, which schedules these consumers to be reidentified over time after classifying them as low confidence.

➤ *Client associations*

Combining all of the data from the aforementioned steps to finally determine "Who took what?" is probably the trickiest issue.

➤ *Pose Prediction*

The tracking of locations Go store cameras must travel across the pixels corresponding to the arm between the objects and a consumer since they see the store top-down rather than from an isometric perspective. Since a straightforward top-down model was insufficient to address this issue, the team decided to create a stick-figure-like model of the customer from the video.

To construct an articulated model of each consumer from the video, a creative new Deep Learning model was required. The joint detection point cloud is constructed using a CNN with a cross-entropy loss function, self-regression is used to create the vectors, and pair-wise regression is used to combine the vectors. This model is quite intriguing on its own. They demonstrated how it may be applied to any video clip to help with a variety of other posture estimation-related difficulties.

➤ *Choosing an action*

The system must correctly take into consideration a scenario where customers can return products to the shelf to prevent billing customers for items they didn't take.

The image up top shows one of the issues in this area. The simple response is that something was taken, yet this is untrue. Instead, a client slid the remaining items farther back on the shelf while placing one back.

Instead of making a simple assumption based on space, the system must count every item on the shelf to address this problem.

➤ *A lengthy tail*

Picking something up from the shelf allows for a huge variety of poses, especially when there are other customers present. For each of them, there isn't enough labeled data to train a model. Scaling the training dataset (in terms of size) would not be achievable even with human labeling.

The team's ambitious initiative to create synthetic activity data using simulators was undertaken to address this issue.

They had to develop virtual people with different looks (including differences in dress, hair, build, height, etc.), cameras, lighting, and shadows, as well as imitate the same camera hardware restrictions, within these simulators.

➤ *ENTRY & EXIT DETECTION*

The next difficulty is establishing the shopping session by determining when individuals enter and leave the store. The elements of this system are as follows:

- a. When you arrive at the store, use a mobile app to scan the QR code. They invested a lot of effort in evaluating the user experience (scanning with phones up or down, handling groups, etc.).
- b. When you scan the QR code, the Association System links your image from the video to your account based on where you are standing at the store entry.

The team faced some extra problems as they worked to put the system into place. First, because users might scan more than once, they had to delete any sessions for which there were no items after a second scan. Customers (particularly families) that wish to buy together but only have one person available to pay present a more challenging issue. The head/payer scans the same code for each customer as they enter the store to enable this. This establishes a session connecting everyone in the group to the same account. The group members are free to exit the store at any time from that point.

➤ *CART, PAYMENT, AND RECEIPTS*

There wasn't much innovation to talk about because these are all much the same as what you can find on Amazon.com. They spent just ten seconds on each of these areas. Naturally, they summed up the presentation with the phrase "It's Day 1 at Amazon Go" and a suggestion that there will soon be significant upgrades, in true Amazon fashion. I left the talk feeling both tremendously optimistic about the future of AI and extremely humbled by how far behind I am in comparison to these kinds of accomplishments.

IV. CASE STUDY

❖ *India's first grocery store without a cashier is Watasale Kochi's startup.*

Naya sale retail pvt ltd, a Kochi-based business, opened India's first cashier-less store, watasale, in the gold souk Grande Mall in Kochi, Kerala, in 2018.

Table 1 Watasale

Startup name	Watasale
Headquarters	Kochi, Kerala
Parent company	Nayasale retail pvt ltd.
Founders	Richu Jose, Rajesh malamal, subash s, Dileep Jacob, Vinci Matthews
Industry	Autonomous retail
Founded	2018
Website	www.watasale.com
No.of employees	12

You may purchase anything via Watasale in only 3 easy steps.

When you enter the store, open the watasale app and scan the special QR code with it. You can now choose the things you need and pay for them using a variety of online payment methods.

You won't have to wait in a big queue for billing, therefore.

- *Launch of Watasale*
 - Operating in Kochi, Kerala, is Watasale.
 - The retail business is the brainchild of five friends and the first of its sort, according to Naya Sale Retail Pvt. Ltd.
 - Due to the project's bootstrapping nature, they had trouble handling the cash.
 - They ultimately succeeded in opening the business after years of cautious preparation and test runs in a garage.
 - Amazon Go and Watasale
 - The Amazon Go served as inspiration for Watasale.
 - They began developing the technology at the beginning of 2015.
 - It happened following Amazon's announcement that it would launch Amazon Go.
 - They used a similar set of technologies to self-driving cars, including touch sensors, AI, and computer vision.
 - Their Watasale prepaid card or wallet will be automatically debited for the cost of the purchased items.
 - After finishing their shopping, customers can simply exit the building without the need for cashiers, lines, checkouts, or scanning.

➤ *App Watasale*

- The shop makes an effort to provide clients with a free checkout experience.
- To enter the store at Watasale, customers must download the Watasale app and scan the generated QR code.
- After they had perfected their algorithms, they turned their attention to developing the physical infrastructure and skeletal framework of the retail store.
- The formation of a core technical team and the appropriate people with knowledge of advanced stages of artificial intelligence was their largest difficulty.

➤ *Used technologies*

To provide clients with a hassle-free shopping experience, Watasale was created as an automated AI-based retail business. It combines technology including touch sensors, artificial intelligence, and computer vision. This store intends to completely transform the customer experience of visiting a retail location and making purchases without waiting in a queue for payment.

With Watasale, the entire shopping process is quick and easy. Customers must download their application and scan the resulting QR code to access the store. Then, all they have to do is keep gathering the things they require, and when they are done shopping, they can just leave the store. The produced bill would be delivered to the customer's phone, and payment could be made using a debit or credit card or by using a mobile wallet.

AI-based systems provide a wide range of additional advantages as well, the most significant of which is the decrease in fraud. Even if the customer tries to conceal the product, it will still be billed in cases of fraud and shoplifting. Due to the system's use of computer vision technology, everything that was taken from the product racks is accounted for. When various processes need to be automated, deep learning becomes essential. Larger-scale versions of the same techniques are used in autonomous warehouses. The workflow procedures include cameras for visual analytics, RFIDs, pressure sensors, and more. All of the devices are used in the activity flow design to create an autonomous experience.

V. RECOMMENDATION AND CONCLUSION

➤ *HOW AI CAN HELP THE HYPERMARKET OF THE FUTURE SUCCEED*

The future of AI in supermarket shopping is bright despite several obstacles. Here are the five steps that will enable you to quickly and painlessly implement AI at your store.

- Describe your expectations for the use of this technology in your organization and the potential returns on your investment. Deloitte suggests using the paradigm described below: Start small, expand quickly, and create incrementally.
- Identify the best talent to take on various specialist jobs. It won't work to throw data scientists into a data lake and expect them to come up with innovative ideas. To create,

transform, and sustain value over the long term, you will need to hire a wide group of internal and external talent.

- Modify organizational culture to foster a positive view of AI. Many workers continue to perceive AI as a terrifying, unknowable black box. Make it clear that the major purpose of AI is to assist and support humans in making wise judgments.
- Sort your data. As grocery stores gain access to information in video format, from social media, and via geo-location apps and devices, the amount of data that AI can use is constantly growing. Many retailers disregard the need for a clear data strategy despite the complexity of the data growing.

➤ *Recommendation*

- Integrate a Hybrid Solar Power facility, integrate technology automation to manage its own Cold Storage, and design, construct, and renovate the current Hyper Market. Then make sure that the fish and vegetable market is temperature-controlled and can support itself.
- The Smart Market operates on Reduced Energy Consumption, which enables the exact synchronization of intelligent technologies, regulatory systems, and systems that guarantee savings for practical demands, such as its light-intensity control switches to maximize electric consumption.

➤ *CONCLUSION*

We can say that this kind of technology investigates the changing dynamic between people and machines, looking at how automation, artificial intelligence, and robots are affecting our daily lives.

The Amazon Go storefront might be crucial to the Just Walk Out technology. Because you will still be charged even if you walk out of a store with an item you stole, this technology may be able to end the enduring issue of retail theft.

Over the past ten years, the retail industry has faced several difficulties that have forced retailers to alter their business plans to stay competitive. Consumer trends like e-commerce have grown significantly over the past few years, and the COVID-19 epidemic has sped up this tendency. While there is no denying that Internet shopping is growing in popularity, numerous research indicates that customers still value visiting actual stores. By fusing the advantages of technological advancement with consumers' preference for the in-person shopping experience, this situation can lead to the widespread adoption of cashier-less stores.

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